

Species CATALOGUE

Developing capacity for Indigenous Community Agroforestry
in the Amadiba area of Eastern Mpondoland

METADATA

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Project Name:

Developing capacity for indigenous community agroforestry in the Amadiba Area of Eastern Mpondoland

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isiMpondo translation:

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Sources of verified information:

Fox, F.W., & Norwood Young, M.E. (1982). Food from the Veld: edible plants of South Africa. Delta Books, Johannesburg. ISBN 0908387326.

PlantZAfrica <http://pza.sanbi.org/>

Useful Tropical Plants <http://tropical.theferns.info/>

World Agroforestry Centre

<https://apps.worldagroforestry.org/treedb/>

The project is a collaboration between the Institute of Natural Resources (INR), Sustaining the Wild Coast (SWC), and Siyasisiza Trust (ST) working together with residents of the Amadiba Coastal Villages in Eastern Mpondoland. Within this collaboration, INR brings the scientific and technical aspects of indigenous agroforestry species, the local SWC team provides leadership within Amadiba and ST brings technical expertise in the locally established agroecology infrastructure.

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The INR project team is grateful to the Amadiba Farmers Forums with support from SWC and ST for organising and facilitating the workshops and planting, including communication, logistics, catering, and coordinating community effort. We are very grateful to the communities for their warm hospitality and participation. We acknowledge the UNDP GEF Small Grants Programme for funding this work.

This catalogue presents information on useful indigenous agroforestry species planted as part of the project in the Amadiba area in South Africa. These plant species naturally occur in the area, many of them bear edible fruits and medicinal parts, and all of them have agroforestry uses like providing shade, windbreaks, or wood.

The catalogue provides information on each of the species on a leaflet. The front left panel of the leaflet describes the natural habitat and characteristics of the plant species, also indicating considerations when planting around homes. The front right panels list the edible, medicinal, agroforestry, and environmental uses of the species. On the back left panel is information on the wider environmental considerations, such as the global distribution of the species and its relationships with wildlife. The back right panels indicate the specific conditions required for the species to grow and reproduce.

This catalogue can be read together with the Plant care manuals developed as part of the project, which provide general guidelines on planting, care and monitoring, sustainable use, and propagation.

KEY TO SYMBOLS

Plant height/canopy spread

Tree

Planting considerations

Ecosystem associations

Fruiting/planting season

Levels

AFRICAN MANGOSTEEN

Garcinia livingstonei (L), African mangosteen (E), amabimbi (X)

The tree occurs widely through the Tropical regions of Africa and is found in scrub, open woodland and forest, up to 1,900m.

The 2.5 cm fruit is produced in clusters from November to January and is eaten raw, juiced or in jams.

The small to medium tree can reach 7m or more, with a spreading habit and dense foliage.

With a moderate canopy and root system, the tree is well-suited near roads, buildings, and utility infrastructure.

FRUITING SEASON			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit contains vitamins A, B and C, for healthy skin, bones, blood and boosts immunity.

The fruit also contains calcium, magnesium and zinc for strong bones and muscles.

The powdered root is used as an aphrodisiac.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The evergreen tree can grow into a valuable shade tree or planted as a windbreak.

The wood is used for making fence poles and tools.

The fruit can be fermented into an alcoholic drink.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The tree attract bees, butterflies, birds and animals, thereby promoting biodiversity.

The tree's dense foliage make it suitable to plant as a hedge.

The drought-tolerant tree can help to stabilise the soil and restore degraded habitats.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/garcinia-livingstonei>
 Photos: iNaturalist, PlantZAfrica,
 Wikimedia Commons

AFRICAN MANGOSTEEN

Garcinia livingstonei (L), African mangosteen (E), amabimbi (X)

The tree is found throughout southern Africa in the Albany thicket, grassland, savanna and woodland biomes.

The nectar-rich flowers attract many insects which pollinate them. The ripe fruits are consumed by various birds and animals which then disperse the seeds.

The tree is dioecious – each tree produces either male or female flowers, and relies on insects for pollination.

It is therefore best to plant multiple individuals close together to promote fruiting.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree prefers a tropical climate with a temperature range between 15°C and 25°C.

Annual rainfall between 800mm and 1,800mm is preferred.

The tree prefers full sun, tolerates semi shade and is cold-sensitive.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The tree can grow in a range of well-drained soils.

It prefers a neutral to slightly acidic pH between 5 and 6.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Fresh seeds should germinate at around 6 months.

Cuttings treated with hormones and truncheons strike readily.

Grafting allows for both male and female flowers on the same plant to promote pollination and fruiting.

Seedlings and young plants should be well-watered.

Growth rate is very slow, and the tree matures after about 2 years from grafts and cuttings, and 4 years from seed.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/garcinia-livingstonei>
 Photos: iNaturalist, PlantAfrica,
 Wikimedia Commons

SGP The GEF
 Small Grants
 Programme

BLADDER NUT

Diospyros whyteana (L), bladder nut (E), umtenatane (X)

The tree is widely spread throughout Southern Africa and is found in evergreen, montane, and scrub forest up to 2,400m.

The tree fruits from January to April and produces 2cm in diameter, single, unique bladder-enclosed nuts that are eaten raw.

The fast-growing evergreen shrub or small tree reaches a height of 3m with a dense, medium-sized canopy.

Its moderate growth habit and root system allows the tree to be planted near buildings, schools, roads, electric lines and water pipes.

FRUITING SEASON				
Dec	Jan	Feb	☀️	
Mar	Apr	May	🌿	
Jun	Jul	Aug	❄️	
Sep	Oct	Nov	🦋	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

It is packed with fibre, protein and amino acids for a healthy digestive system.

Bark extracts are used in traditional remedies for menstrual pain, impotency, and infertility.

Leaf and root infusions are used to treat skin rashes.

Roasted seeds have been used as a coffee substitute.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The bitter fruit is not commonly eaten and primarily used for dyes.

The wood is used for making fence poles, tools and furniture.

The plant responds well to clipping and makes an excellent hedge.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The flowers attract pollinating insects such as bees and butterflies, and in turn, attract birds.

The shrubby growth form provides nesting sites for some birds.

The dense shrub can be planted for shelter and as a windbreak.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/diospyros-whyteana>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

BLADDER NUT

Diospyros whyteana (L), bladder nut (E), umtenatane (X)

The bladder nut originates in Southern Africa and is found in the Albany thicket, fynbos, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna biomes.

The plant has a moderate biodiversity value as a pollinating plant for insects, food for game and livestock that browse the foliage, and birds that consume the fruit.

The shrub is dioecious, with each individual plant producing either male or female flowers, thereby relying on insects for pollination.

Plants should be planted together in groups to promote pollination and fruiting.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The plant is suited to a warm and temperate range of climates from 10°C to 35°C.

It is best suited in areas that receive moderate annual rainfall.

The versatile plant can tolerate full sun or shade.

It is resistant to drought and frost: flexi is sexy!

SOIL CONDITIONS

The plant prefers a sandy, loamy soil that drains well.

A neutral pH of 5 - 7 is preferred for ideal growing conditions.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

The plant is grown from seed which must be scratched/scarified before sowing.

Seeds usually germinate between 4 to 8 weeks.

Seedlings and young plants require moderate watering for optimal growth.

The slow growing shrub will achieve a growth rate of about 30cm per year

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/diospyros-whyteana>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

BROOM CLUSTER FIG

Ficus sur (L), broom cluster fig (E), umthumbu, amakhiwane (X)

The broom cluster fig occurs across South Africa along riverbanks, and in riverine forest, woodland and wooded grassland, up to 2,500m.

Fruits form profusely in clusters, each fruit about 5cm in diameter, and can be eaten raw or dried.

The tree grows about 20m high and spreads a wide canopy with strong hanging and aggressive underground roots.

Because of its growth habit, it is best planted in open spaces, away from power and water lines, and buildings and roads.

Planting considerations

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

It is packed with fibre - filling, and healthy for the digestive system.

It contains calcium, iron, and phosphorus, strengthening bones and blood.

The fruit can easily be used to make delicious juices, jams and preserves.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

It can provide shade for humans and plants with its large and wide canopy.

Its branches can provide soft wood for carving, drums, and small wooden implements.

The bark can be used to make rope, and is also used in traditional medicine.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

It attracts wasps to pollinate the flowers, thereby supporting their reproduction.

Birds feed on its fruits, and also on the insects that are attracted to the tree.

Mammals like bats and monkeys eat its fruits and spread the seeds.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/ficus-sur>

Photos: Glence Ebedes, iSpotnature

BROOM CLUSTER FIG

Ficus sur (L), broom cluster fig (E), umthumbu, amakhiwane (X)

The tree originates from Southern Africa, and occurs in the Albany thicket, fynbos, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, Nama Karoo, savanna, and Succulent Karoo biomes.

The caterpillars of butterflies and moths feed on the leaves or roots. Bats, birds, elephants, and monkeys enjoy the ripe fruits.

Pollination is done by wasps, who lay their eggs inside the fruit. It grows between the branches of a tall tree, then drops its roots to the ground.

Because it is visited by wasps, make sure to plant it away from the house.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree thrives in warm conditions of between 16°C and 21°C.

It grows best in areas with a moderate to high annual rainfall of 800mm - 1,800mm.

The tree requires full sun, and will quickly shade plants underneath.

It can tolerate light frost, but will require protection when young.

SOIL CONDITIONS

Grows well in sandy, loamy, and clayey soils.

Strong roots can find footing and stability quickly, even in windy, muddy places.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Can be grown from cleaned seed, which germinates in about a week.

Can also be grown from cuttings taken in spring.

Regular watering in the first four years in areas of moderate rainfall; will take care of itself in high rainfall areas.

Grows about half to 1m a year, matures at four years of age.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/ficus-sur>

Photos: Glenice Ebedes, iSpotnature

BUFFALO THORN

Ziziphus mucronata (L), buffalo thorn (E), umphafa (X)

The tree is found across southern Africa in a range of habitats such as woodlands, open scrubland, rocky slopes and grasslands, up to 2,000m.

Although the tree does produce fruit, it is not very tasty. The tree is valued for its other properties.

The large tree grows up to 10m with a spreading canopy, and branches are armed with thorns.

Its non-aggressive root system makes it suitable for planting near schools and water pipes, but not power lines or roads on account of its height and thorny canopy spread.

Planting considerations

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

It is a rich source of calcium, iron, magnesium and potassium that promote bone and blood health.

The roots are sometimes used as a painkiller.

The bark and leaves are used for healing and applied as a poultice.

The seed is sometimes roasted as a substitute for coffee.

The sweet powdery pulp around the seed can be pulped as a nutritious porridge.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The leaves are used as a fodder for livestock.

Branches are used in burial rites and ancestral spirit interactions.

The timber is used for fuelwood, and for making fence poles and tools.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The tree is a valuable nectar source for insects, perfect for beekeeping.

With its dense thorny foliage, it can be planted as an impenetrable live fence to keep livestock out.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/vangueria-infausta>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

BUFFALO THORN

Ziziphus mucronata (L), buffalo thorn (E), umphafa (X)

The tree originates in Africa and is found in the Albany thicket, fynbos, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, Nama Karoo, savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes.

It plays a significant role in the ecosystem as a habitat for wildlife and a food source for birds, game and livestock that eat the leaves and fruit.

The flowers are pollinated by bees and seed is distributed by birds and animals that eat the fruit.

Because it attracts a variety of insects, birds and animals, plant it away from the house to keep friendly relations with the wildlife.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree favours a mild to temperate climate with a temperature range of 12°C to 30°C.

It prefers an annual rainfall between 440mm and 1,200mm.

The tree grows best when planted in full sun.

This adaptable tree can withstand frost and drought.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The tree favours sandy and loamy soils, but can tolerate most other well-drained soils.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

As seed cannot be stored it is best to use fresh seed.

Seed needs to be cracked from the nut and soaked overnight in hot water before sowing.

Seed germination usually takes up to 2 weeks.

Young plants require moderate watering.

The slow-growing plant achieves up to 30cm per year.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/vangueria-infausta>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

CORAL TREE

Erythrina lysistemon (L), coral tree (E), umsinsi (X)

The tree occurs across southern Africa, on coastal sand dunes, in wooded grassland, deciduous woodlands, and bushland, up to 1,950m.

The fruit is not edible and comes in the form of 150-200mm slender seed pods, borne in clusters from October to December.

The tree takes its name from the striking crimson flowers in spring. It reaches around 7m and higher under favourable conditions.

With a moderate root system and canopy, the tree's growth habit allows it to be planted near buildings, roads and utility infrastructure.

SEEDING SEASON			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

A boiled infusion of leaves and bark is believed to help with childbirth.

Leaves contain anti-inflammatory and anti-bacterial compounds and are used for treating wounds.

A mixtue of the leaves is used in treating ear ache.

Concoctions of the roots are used to treat sprains, and the bark is used topically in the treatment of sores and wounds.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

Regarded as royal trees, they are planted on the graves of Zulu chiefs.

The seeds, also known as "lucky beans", are used as beads.

The flowering of the trees is a good signal to plant crops.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

Birds such as barbets and woodpeckers nest in the trunks of dead trees and swarms of bees often inhabit hollow trunks.

With its thorny, low-growing branches, the tree can be planted as a live fence.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/erythrina-lysistemon>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

CORAL TREE

Erythrina lysistemon (L), coral tree (E), umsinsi (X)

The tree originates from southern Africa and occurs in the Indian Ocean coastal belt biome.

The tree provides nectar to insects and birds, vervet monkeys eat the flower buds, several game species graze on the leaves, rhinos, elephants and baboons eat the bark, and bush pigs eat the roots.

The flowers are pollinated by insects and birds. The brown-headed parrot eats and disperses the seed.

The deciduous tree can be planted where you need sun in winter and shade in summer.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree tolerates a temperature range between 10°C and 35°C.

It prefers to grow in areas of high summer rainfall.

It is able to grow in full sun and semi shade.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The tree can grow in a range of well-drained soils.

Its root nodules help to fix nitrogen into the soil.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Seeds should be soaked overnight before being sown, and are slow to germinate.

It can be easily grown from cuttings treated with hormones in late spring to summer, and by truncheons in late winter to spring.

The tree requires moderate watering while young.

It grows rapidly under optimum conditions, 1 - 1.5m per year.

Young trees are sensitive to frost and will require protection in colder areas.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/erythrina-lysistemon>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

CROSS-BERRY

Grewia occidentalis (L), cross-berry (E), ilalanyathi, umnqabaza (X)

The shrub is found across South Africa, especially the east coast, and in various habitats, from the Karoo, coastal dune bush, evergreen Afromontane forests, and savanna-bushveld, up to 2,500m.

The 1 cm four-lobed fruit is produced in clusters from January to May and can be eaten raw, juiced or in a jam.

It grows as a shrub or small tree and can reach 3m under ideal conditions.

With a moderate root system, low fruit and leaf litter intensity, the plant is suitable near buildings, roads, water pipes and electricity lines.

FRUITING SEASON			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit contains vitamins A, B and C to promote general health, vitality and immunity.

A rich source of calcium, iron, potassium and zinc to promote healthy blood, bones and muscle.

It contains amino acids, which all body cells need to perform their functions.

Bark soaked in hot water is used to treat wounds.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The shrub provides fodder for livestock as the leaves are browsed by cattle and goats.

Planted in a row, they create an effective windbreak and screen.

The wood is used for making fence poles and tools.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The plant attracts bees and butterflies, both crucial pollinators.

The leaves are browsed by rhino, giraffe, and grey duiker.

This versatile tree is resistant to drought and frost: flexi is sexy!

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/grewia-occidentalis>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

CROSS-BERRY

Grewia occidentalis (L), bow-wood, cross-berry, star-flower (E), ilalanyathi, umnqabaza (X)

The shrub originates in central Africa and occurs in the Albany thicket, fynbos, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, Nama Karoo, savanna, and Succulent Karoo biomes.

The nectar-rich flowers attract insects. The leaves are a food source for butterfly larvae, goats, cattle, rhino, giraffe, nyala and grey duiker. Ripe fruits are relished by birds and animals.

The flowers are pollinated by insects and seeds are dispersed by birds and animals.

It produces lots of seeds which set easily, and many seedlings may be found nearby.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The shrub tolerates a range of climate conditions but thrives in warmer temperatures, between 20°C and 38°C.

It grows in areas of high rainfall and can also withstand drought.

The shrub does well in full sun or semi shade.

SOIL CONDITIONS

Grows well in various soils, including sandy, medium loamy, and heavy clay.

It can tolerate an acid, neutral, and alkaline pH.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Soak fresh seeds overnight before sowing from January - April.

Seeds germinate readily between 2 and 6 weeks.

Can also be grown from cuttings treated with hormones taken in summer and autumn.

Young plants and seedlings require a fair amount of watering.

They are fast growing but slow down as they reach maturity.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/grewia-occidentalis>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

FLAT CROWN

Albizia adianthifolia (L), Flat crown (E), umgadankawu, umhlandlothi (X)

The tree occurs in tropical areas and the northern parts of South Africa, coastal and low-altitude forests, forest margins, open forest and ravines, between 250m and 450m.

The fruit is not edible, but seeds that are produced in pods, can be turned into a sauce.

The fast-growing tree reaches a height of 10m and is an ideal shade tree with a large canopy. It is therefore not suitable to plant near power lines.

Its moderate roots and low leaf litter make it suitable to plant near water pipes, and dwellings.

Planting considerations

SEEDING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

An emetic from the bark is used to treat skin diseases and also bronchitis.

Root extracts are applied to inflamed eyes and skin disorders.

The bark is used as a remedy for internal parasites and tapeworm.

The powdered bark is used to treat headaches and sinusitis.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The wide, spreading canopy makes it an ideal shade tree, for shelter and windbreaks.

Because of its shape, it is a popular ornamental tree.

The timber is extensively used in building and construction, carvings and also fuel.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The tree is important to pollinators, and butterfly larva feed on the leaves.

The root nodules help improve the soil by fixing nitrogen.

It can be used as an effective soil erosion control method.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/albizia-adianthifolia-var-adianthifolia>

Photos: PlantZAfrica, Wikimedia

FLAT CROWN

Albizia adianthifolia (L), Flat crown (E), umgadankawu, umhlandlothi (X)

The tree originates from tropical, Northern South Africa, and occurs in the Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna biomes.

The tree flowers in spectacular profusion and is a haven for insects, and a food source for butterfly larvae.

The tree is easily pollinated by insects as it yields clusters of seed pods.

Fresh seeds can be stored for up to 3 months before planting.

Because it attracts insects make sure to plant it away from the house.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

Optimum growing temperature is 22°C to 28°C, but can tolerate 15°C to 34°C.

It thrives under high annual rainfall conditions of 1,500mm to 2,500mm, but will tolerate extremes of 900mm to 4,000mm.

The tree grows best in full sun and is sensitive to frost.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The tree grows best in humus-rich, sandy and loamy soils.

Optimal tree growth requires a neutral pH range of 4 to 7.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Seeds should be soaked in hot water overnight before being planted the next day.

Transplant seedlings into larger pots or directly into the ground when they have two leaves.

Seedlings and young trees should be watered regularly.

An annual growth rate of between 1m and 2m is likely under optimum conditions.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/albizia-adianthifolia-var-adianthifolia>

Photos: PlantZAfrica, iSpotnature

FOREST NUM-NUM

Carissa bispinosa (L), Forest num-num (E), amathungula (X)

The forest num-num occurs across southern Africa in woodland, woodland fringes, and on maritime dunes, up to 1,600m.

The 1cm-fruit forms in clusters, between March and October, and can be eaten raw, juiced or to make delicious jam, jelly, and even wine.

The medium-sized plant grows about 3m high into a thorny bush or scrambling shrub with a dense compact canopy.

Due to its low leaf litter and root intensity, it can be planted around power and water lines and near buildings and roads.

FRUITING SEASON			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

It is packed with vitamin C, which helps maintain a healthy brain, hair, hormones, and skin.

It is a great source of magnesium and phosphorus, promoting muscle and bone function.

The fruit is rich in antioxidants that assist with overall good health and healing.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

Its dense, thorny foliage makes for a neat compact hedge or impenetrable live fence to keep livestock out.

The roots are used to cure pain, and chest, eye, stomach, and viral ailments in traditional medicine.

Planted close together they make ideal windbreaks, as they are highly resistant to strong winds.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

Insects, especially butterflies, visit the flowers.

Birds love its fruit, and some also like to nest in the protective branches of the shrub.

The tough shrub is evergreen and is drought-resistant.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-bispinosa>
 Photos: PlantZAfrica, iNaturalist,
 Wikimedia Commons

FOREST NUM-NUM

Carissa bispinosa (L), Forest num-num (E), amathungula (X)

The forest num-num originates from the East coast of southern Africa and is found in the Albany thicket, fynbos, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, savanna, Succulent Karoo and Nama Karoo biomes.

The leaves are a food source for butterflies, the sweet flowers attract insects and birds and mammals consume the fruit.

Pollination is performed by bees and seed is dispersed by fruit-eating birds.

Collect fresh seeds for planting from ripened fruit by removing the pulp from around the seed.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The shrub prefers a tropical and sub-tropical climate with an average temperature of 25°C.

It is ideally suited to moderate to high rainfall (800 to 1,200 mm), but will tolerate extremes of 600 mm to 1,800 mm.

It prefers full sun and will tolerate some light shade.

SOIL CONDITIONS

Thrives in sandy, loam soils and will tolerate other well-drained soils.

It is most suited to a pH level of 6.5 but can tolerate values between 5 and 8.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

The shrub can be grown from seed or from half-ripe heel cuttings treated with hormones.

Seeds harvested from a healthy plant will germinate within 2 months.

Seedlings and young plants require little watering.

Growth rates vary from 300mm to 1.2m annually and reaches maturity in 2-3 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-bispinosa>
 Photos: PlantZAfrica, iNaturalist,
 Wikimedia Commons

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GINGER BUSH

Tetradenia riparia (L), ginger bush, misty plume bush (E), iboza (X)

The shrub is found on the east coast of Southern Africa, along riverbanks, in forest margins, dry wooded valleys, hillsides and areas where there is little frost, up to 1,800m.

Fruit is borne in the form of a pod that contains seeds on female plants, and are not edible.

The fast-growing plant forms a shrub up to 3m that produces attractive spays of mauve flowers in late winter.

The plant can be grown near buildings, roads, water pipes and power lines due to a non-aggressive root system and modest canopy.

SEEDING SEASON			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The plant is valued for its medicinal properties and has been used for centuries to relieve respiratory issues, stomach aches and headaches.

The crushed leaves are infused and used in decoctions to treat a wide range of illnesses such as diarrhoea, dropsy, fever, flu, malaria and dengue fever, yaws, and also toothache.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The plant is an attractive ornamental during winter when spikes of pale mauve flowers transform the shrub into a misty mauve cloud when little else is blooming.

The flowering stems do well in water for flower arranging.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The nectar rich flowers attract many species of pollinating insects and it is an important forage plant for bees in winter months.

Numerous insectivorous birds are attracted by the many insects that visit the flowers.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/tetradenia-riparia>
 Photos: Glence Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

GINGER BUSH

Tetradenia riparia (L), ginger bush, misty plume bush (E), iboza (X)

The plant originates in Central and Southern Africa and occurs in the savanna biome.

It contributes to biodiversity as a pollinator plant for insects, especially bees, and as a food source for butterfly larvae.

The shrub is dioecious, with each individual plant only producing either male or female flowers.

Insects pollinate the flowers that develop into fruit on the female plants.

It is best to plant multiple shrubs together to promote flowering, fruiting and pollination.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

- The plant prefers a warm, subtropical to tropical climate.
- Areas with a low annual rainfall are best suited.
- The plant thrives when planted in full sun.
- It can tolerate minimal frost and is sensitive to cold temperatures.

SOIL CONDITIONS

- It prefers well-drained loamy, sandy or slightly clay soils.
- It prefers soils with a neutral pH of about 6,5.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

- It is best grown from cuttings are treated with hormones. These strike easily and can be planted throughout the year.
- The shrub requires moderate watering in summer, and less in winter.
- Once established, it grows about 80cm per year, and will flower in its first year.
- The plant benefits from pruning after the flowering season.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/tetradenia-riparia>

Photos: Glenice Ebedes,
Wikimedia Commons

KEI APPLE

Dovyalis caffra (L), Kei apple (E), umqokolo (X)

The Kei Apple occurs in the eastern and southern regions of South Africa, and grows in dry areas, wooded grassland, and forest edges, up to 2,450m.

The fruits form profusely in clusters, each fruit about 6cm in diameter, from November to January, and can be eaten raw, juiced or preserved.

The tree-shrub grows about 4m high, and spreads its dense branches and thorns rapidly.

With its moderate height and low leaf litter, it can be planted near water and power lines, buildings and roads.

FRUITING SEASON			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

It contains Vitamins A and B for the eyes, skin, hair, hormones and healthy brain function.

It is packed with Vitamin C (seven times that of an orange) for immune system support.

It is rich in calcium and phosphorus, strengthening bones and blood.

It contains protein and fibre, supporting muscle and gut health.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The leaves and stalks are used as fodder, particularly for cattle in the dry season.

It attracts bees to pollinate its flowers, perfect for beekeeping.

It is resistant to drought and frost: flexi is sexy!

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

It makes a great hedge or live fence to keep animals and livestock out.

Birds feed on its fruits, and also on the insects attracted to the tree.

Mammals like antelope and monkeys eat its fruits and spread the seeds.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<http://pza.sanbi.org/dovyalis-caffra>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

KEI APPLE

Dovyalis caffra (L), Kei apple (E), umqokolo (X)

The Kei apple originates from Southern Africa and occurs in the Albany thicket, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes.

The plant is a food source for insects (flowers), while birds and mammals consume the fruit.

The plant is dioecious with separate male and female flowers and is pollinated by insects.

It is best planted in clumps to promote fruiting.

As it attracts birds, insects and animals, plant it away from the house, to keep friendly relations with the wildlife.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The plant tolerates a wide range of climates and prefers a warm to tropical temperature, with ranges from 10°C to 35°C.

It grows best in areas with an annual rainfall of between 700mm and 1,300mm.

The tree-shrub prefers full sun, is drought tolerant and will also do well in partial shade.

SOIL CONDITIONS

Kei apple prefers to be planted deep in sandy, loamy soils that are well-drained.

A pH range of 5 - 7 is preferred for optimum growing conditions.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

The plant can be grown from seed that is cleaned and dried in the shade.

The seeds will germinate between 18 and 20 days.

It can also be propagated from hardwood cuttings (treated).

The plant has an annual growth rate of 60cm a year and reaches maturity after 4 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<http://pza.sanbi.org/dovyalis-caffra>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, PlantZAfrica

LALA PALM

Hyphaene coriacea (L), lala palm, ilala palm, gingerbread tree, fan palm (E), ilala (X)

The lala palm is found along the east coast of Southern Africa, typically near rivers, on sandy banks and coastal dunes.

The 5cm fruit is borne in clusters throughout the year. The fruit ripens over two years and is made into a milk or juice.

It grows into a 5m multi-stemmed tree with large chunky leaves. All parts of the palm are used, making it a highly versatile plant.

Its non-invasive root system, moderate height and leaf litter make it suitable to be planted near buildings, water pipes, power lines and roads.

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

It is a rich source of vitamins B and C for brain and blood health and for immunity.

Fruit pulp is used to treat stomach complaints and intestinal cleansing.

Tender leaves can be eaten as a vegetable.

Crown sap is tapped for milk and fermented into an alcoholic drink.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The leaves are used as fodder for livestock.

The wood is used for fence poles, tools and fuelwood.

Fibre from the leaves are used for weaving baskets and bags.

Ornaments are carved from the seeds that resemble vegetable ivory.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The fruit is a food source for elephants and baboons.

The spiny bases of old leaves provide nesting sites for birds.

It is useful for soil stabilisation and combating erosion.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hyphaene-coriacea>
 Photos: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

LALA PALM

Hyphaene coriacea (L), lala palm, ilala palm, gingerbread tree, fan palm (E), ilala (X)

The lala palm originates on the eastern coast of Southern Africa and typically occurs in the Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna biomes.

Elephants and baboons feed on the fruit and birds nest in the leaves.

It is dioecious, with separate male and female trees. Plant trees in clumps to promote fruiting.

Pollination is performed by insects and the seed is dispersed by animals.

Because it attracts insects and animals, plant it in big open spaces, away from the house.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

- It grows in semi-arid and hot, dry areas with temperatures above 10°C.
- It tolerates rainfall between 250mm and 1,500mm annually.
- The tree prefers to be planted in full sun.
- The hardy evergreen tree is drought tolerant.

SOIL CONDITIONS

- It grows in alluvial sands and in sandy, clay, and loam soils.
- It prefers an alkaline pH of greater than 7.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

- Fruit must be cracked open to release the seed before sowing.
- Seeds planted in spring and mid-summer or in autumn, germinate easily within 14 to 180 days.
- Suckers can also be taken from a parent plant.
- Young plants and seedlings need to be well-watered.
- It is slow growing, with about one new leaf a year.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hyphaene-coriacea>
 Photos: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

NATAL FIG

Ficus natalensis (L), Natal fig, forest fig (E), umpayi, amakhiwane (X)

The tree occurs throughout eastern Africa in wet and dry forest and thickets, riverine and ground-water forests, and in higher rainfall woodland and savanna, up to 2,200m.

The 1cm fruit is produced in clusters from July to December, and is eaten raw, juiced, or in a jam.

It grows into a large structural tree of 20m with aerial roots and a dense, spreading canopy.

Due to its aggressive root system, height and growth habit, the tree must not be grown near buildings, water pipes and power lines.

Planting considerations

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit contains calcium, iron, magnesium, phosphorus and potassium which help bones and muscles.

Leaves are used for gastronomical complaints and also applied to wounds.

An extract of the root is used as an eye treatment.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS AND FIELDS

The tree has an immense canopy, perfect as a shade tree.

The bark is used to make barkcloth, a renewable material used in the fashion industry.

The bark is also used as medicine for whooping cough, influenza and to induce lactation.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

Many insects and birds feed on the nectar, and the fruit is eaten by birds and bats.

Wasps pollinate the flowers, and nest in the fruit, thereby supporting their reproduction.

It is evergreen, wind-tolerant and can be planted as a windbreak.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/ficus-natalensis>
 Photos: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

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NATAL FIG

Ficus natalensis (L), Natal fig, forest fig (E), umpayi, amakhiwane (X)

The tree originates in Africa and is found in the savanna and woodland biomes.

It contributes to the ecosystem as a food source for insects, especially wasps, birds and bats.

Pollination is done by wasps, who lay their eggs inside the fruit. It grows between the branches of a tall tree, then drops its roots to the ground.

It can be propagated by cuttings and seeds from September to November.

Because it is visited by wasps, make sure to plant it away from the house.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree grows best under tropical and sub tropical conditions.

This adaptable tree can grow in a range of areas with either low or high rainfall.

It prefers full sun and tolerates semi-shade.

The tree is low-maintenance and is also drought-tolerant.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The tree grows best in well-drained soils and in areas with a high water table.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Seed collected and cleaned from ripe fruit will germinate in 15 - 90 days.

Can also be grown from cuttings treated with hormones. These strike easily and will be established in 12 - 18 months.

Regular watering in the first four years in areas of moderate rainfall; will take care of itself in high rainfall areas.

Fast-growing, about half to 1m a year, matures at four years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/ficus-natalensis>
 Photos: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

NATAL MAHOGANY

Trichilia emetica (L), Natal mahogany (E), umkuhlu (X)

The tree occurs across Southern Africa, growing in riverine forest and bushveld up to 1,800m.

The fruit is borne in clusters in the form of a woody capsule, each 2cm in diameter, from January to May. These contain 3-6 seeds that are covered in a fleshy red aril, and are eaten cooked.

The medium to large evergreen tree reaches 20m with a dense spreading canopy.

Its height and heavy fruiting makes it not suitable for planting near power lines and roads but is suitable near water pipes and schools.

Planting considerations

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

It contains calcium, iron, magnesium and important rare trace elements for overall health.

The bark is used to treat pneumonia, epilepsy and leprosy.

It is used as an emetic or enema to treat intestinal ailments.

The roots are used to treat colds, cirrhosis, river blindness, ascariasis and dysmenorrhoea.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS AND FIELDS

The tree is planted as a shade tree and windbreak.

The mature timber is valued in furniture making.

The wood is used as fuelwood and for making fence poles and tools.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The tree is used for stabilising the soil and to combat erosion.

The seed oil cake is used as a natural fertiliser.

The dense foliage provides a habitat to birds and bats.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/trichilia-emetica>
 Photos: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

NATAL MAHOGANY

Trichilia emetica (L), Natal mahogany (E), umkuhlu (X)

The tree originates in Southern Africa and is commonly found in the savanna biome.

The fruits and seeds are eaten by monkeys and birds and the leaves are browsed by animals.

The flowers are pollinated by bees, butterflies, and other insects. The seeds are dispersed by the birds and animals that eat the seeds and fruit.

Propagation is through seeds and cuttings and can be planted all year round.

Make sure to plant the tree in wide open spaces, and away from the house as it attracts various insects and animals.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree prefers a mild to temperate climate with a range of between 18°C and 32°C.

It prefers annual rainfall of at least 600mm.

It grows best in full sun but also tolerates some shade.

SOIL CONDITIONS

It grows best in loamy and other well-drained soils.

It prefers a neutral pH of between 5 and 7.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Seed must be sown fresh and not dried to germinate successfully.

Germination usually takes place between 10 and 20 days.

Semi-hard cuttings treated with hormones can be taken from a mature tree.

The tree has moderate water requirements.

The tree grows at a rate of 1,5m per year under optimum conditions and reaches maturity at 6 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/trichilia-emetica>

Photos: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

NATAL MILKPLUM

Englerophytum natalense (L), Natal milkplum, silver-leaved milkplum (E), umthongwane (X)

The plant is found on the east coast of southern Africa, and occurs in rainforest, riverine, ravine and coastal forests and in forests, up to 1,800m.

The 1.5cm single fruits are borne from November to January and are eaten raw.

This medium to large evergreen tree can grow up to 15m tall with a moderate canopy.

With a moderate root system the tree is suited to be planted near buildings and roads but not near water and power lines because of its height and high leaf litter.

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit is a rich source of vitamin C - as much as an apple, to promote cellular function and immunity.

It also contains calcium, iron, and potassium for blood, bone and muscle health, and is also rich in amino acids.

Concoctions of the roots are used to treat gastric ailments and stomach aches.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The tree can grow into a valuable shade tree and can be planted as a windbreak.

The strong and durable timber is used for making fence poles, tools, in carpentry and as fuelwood.

A highly decorative tree that does well in shady areas and will tolerate periods of waterlogging.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The flowers attract insects, including bees and butterflies, and in turn attracts birds to the garden.

The tree can be strategically planted as a highly effective measure for controlling erosion.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/englerophytum-natalense>

Photos: PlantZAfrica, Wikimedia Commons

NATAL MILKPLUM

Englerophytum natalense (L), Natal milkplum (E), umthongwane (X)

The tree originates on the east coast of Southern Africa and is typically found in the grassland and savanna biomes.

The tree is a significant food source for wildlife – sunbirds feed on flowers, butterfly larvae feed on the leaves and the fruit is consumed by monkeys, bush pigs and fruit-eating birds.

Plants are slow growing and need to be nurtured with moderate watering, shade and warmth.

Because it attracts birds, insects and animals, plant it away from the house, to keep friendly relations with the wildlife.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree prefers a temperate climate and tolerates a temperature range between 10°C and 35°C.

Being water-loving, it prefers areas of high annual rainfall.

The tree is better suited to shade or semi shade.

It is sensitive to frost and needs protection in colder areas.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The tree grows in loamy, silty and slightly clay soils with good water retaining properties.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

The tree can be grown straight away from fresh, cleaned seed.

Seeds germinate quickly between 2 and 3 weeks.

It can also be grown from cuttings treated with hormones, and from truncheons.

Seedlings and young plants require to be watered often.

The slow-growing tree achieves about 300-400mm per year and it reaches maturity at 6 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/englerophytum-natalense>

Photos: PlantZAfrica, Wikimedia Commons

NATAL PLUM

Carissa macrocarpa (L), big num-num, Natal plum (E), amathungula (X)

The Natal plum occurs on the eastern seaboard of Africa and Southern Africa, typically in coastal bush, coastal forests and on sand dunes, at various altitudes and latitudes.

The single fruit of about 5cm, from March to October, is sought-after and eaten raw, juiced, or in a jam.

The low-growing shrub produces dense foliage and rarely exceeds 2m.

Its low growth habit, leaf litter and root intensity, makes it suitable to plant near buildings, roads and utility infrastructure.

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

It is packed with vitamin C, which helps maintain a healthy brain, hair, hormones, and skin.

It is a great source of magnesium and phosphorus, promoting muscle and bone function.

It is packed with fibre and protein for energy and a healthy digestive system.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The fruits are valued as ingredients in delicious jams and jellies.

It attracts bees to pollinate its flowers, perfect for beekeeping.

Because of its dazzling flowering display and attractive foliage, it is a highly ornamental and useful addition to the garden.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The flowers and fruits attract many butterflies and birds.

With its hard, Y-shaped thorns, this fast-growing shrub can be grown as an attractive and impenetrable security hedge.

The tough shrub is evergreen and is drought-resistant.

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-macrocarpa>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

NATAL PLUM

Carissa macrocarpa (L), big num-num, Natal plum (E), amathungula (X)

The Natal plum originates on the eastern coast of Southern Africa and is found in the Albany thicket and Indian Ocean coastal belt biomes.

It contributes to biodiversity as a rich food source for bees who feed on the nectar from the flowers, and birds that consume the fruit.

The shrub is dioecious, with each individual plant only producing either male or female flowers, relying on insects to pollinate the flowers.

It is therefore best to plant multiple individuals close together to promote fruiting.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The plant tolerates a range of climates from 23°C to 28°C, but can tolerate extreme temperatures between 10°C and 34°C.

It prefers annual rainfall of between 800mm and 1,200mm, but tolerates between 600mm and 1,800mm.

The plant prefers full sun and will tolerate semi shade.

Preferring warmer conditions, it is sensitive to frost.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The shrub prefers a sandy, loamy soil that drains well.

It will tolerate a pH level between 5 and 8.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Propagation can be from seeds, cuttings treated with hormones, or from layering.

Young plants require moderate watering.

The plant will achieve a moderate growth of 700-1000mm per year and will reach maturity after about 3 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-macrocarpa>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

NATAL WILD BANANA

Strelitzia nicolai (L), Natal wild banana (E), skamanga, ikhamanga (X)

The tree is found on the east coast of Southern Africa and occurs in coastal dune vegetation and evergreen forests.

The fruit is borne in the form of woody seed pods, in autumn and winter. Immature seeds are edible and tasty, in moderation.

The multi-stemmed tree reaches 7m, with large leaves spreading into a fan-shaped crown.

It is suitable for planting near electric lines, roads and in public places, but away from water pipes and buildings due to its aggressive root system.

SEEDING SEASON			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit pods are not edible, but the immature seeds can be ground into flour, mixed with water and baked into a cookie or fritter.

The seeds are a rich source of natural fibre, which is good for digestive health.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The leaf stalks are dried and used to make rope for building fish pens and huts.

Planted close together in rows the trees would form an effective windbreak.

The large tree can be planted as an ornamental specimen with its large leaves and striking flowers.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The spectacular flowers attract many pollinators, including birds, bees and butterflies.

The dense clumps at the base of the tree provide shelter for tree frogs, ducks and birds.

Some caterpillars spin a silk shelter in between the leaves.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/strelitzia-nicolai>
 Photos: Glence Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

NATAL WILD BANANA

Strelitzia nicolai (L), Natal wild banana (E), skamanga, ikhamanga (X)

The tree originates on the east coast of Southern Africa and is found in the Indian Ocean coastal belt biome.

Insects eat and nest in the leaves, monkeys, birds and blue duiker feed on the flowers, and birds and monkeys consume parts of the fruit or seed.

Pollination is performed by birds, particularly by sunbirds. The tree is mostly propagated through suckers that grow from the parent plant.

Because it attracts a host of birds, insects and animals, make sure to plant it in open spaces, away from the house.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

- The plant prefers the temperature range between 18°C and 29°C.
- It grows best in areas with a high annual rainfall.
- The tree prefers to be planted in full sun.
- This hardy, evergreen tree is frost tolerant.

SOIL CONDITIONS

- The plant tolerates a variety of well-draining soils.
- It prefers to grow in soil with a pH of between 6 and 7.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

- The most effective propagation technique is taking suckers from a mature plant all year round.
- To grow from seed, remove from the enclosed orange arils, and soak overnight before sowing.
- Young plants need to be watered regularly.
- The fast-growing tree reaches maturity from 4 years in optimal growing conditions.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/strelitzia-nicolai>

Photos: Glenice Ebedes,
Wikimedia Commons

NUM-NUM

Carissa edulis (L), simple-spined num-num (E), amathungula (X)

The simple-spined num-num is found in central and southern Africa, typically in deciduous forest and coastal thickets, up to 2,000m.

The 1cm fruit are produced in clusters between December and February and are consumed raw, juiced, or in a jam.

The dense shrub may reach a height of 5m under optimum growth conditions. It makes a superb background plant due to its scrambling nature and masses of sweet-scented flowers.

With a low root and leaf litter intensity, the shrub can be planted near schools and buildings, roads and utility lines.

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

It is packed with vitamin C, for the brain, hair, hormones and skin.

It is an abundant source of calcium, iron, magnesium and zinc that promote bone and blood health.

Roots are used various forms in the treatment of cancer, malaria and indigestion, and is widely used as a painkiller and chest remedy.

The fruits help in the treatment of dysentery.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The spiny shrub can be planted as live fence or as a security hedge.

The wood is sometimes used for fuel, especially in colder or remote areas.

The fruit can be fermented to make a wine, or vinegar if fermented longer.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

Some birds like to build their nests within the dense spines.

The fruit and leaves are eaten by a host of birds, baboons, bushpig, monkeys and many buck species.

The plant provides protection for small animals and reptiles.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-edulis>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, PlantZAfrica

NUM-NUM

Carissa edulis (L), simple-spined num-num (E), amathungula (X)

The shrub originates from tropical Africa and it occurs in the Indian Ocean coastal belt biome.

It is a biodiversity powerhouse – birds, baboons, bushpig, monkeys, kudu, nyala, bushbuck, impala and grey duiker like the fruit and foliage – while birds and reptiles seek refuge in its dense canopy.

Pollination is performed by bees and its seed is dispersed by fruit-eating birds and mammals.

Seed can be stored for up to 12 months.

Because it attracts birds, insects and animals, plant it away from the house, to keep friendly relations with the wildlife.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The shrub tolerates a wide range of climates but prefers a warm to tropical temperature, between 19°C and 30°C.

It grows best with an annual rainfall between 1,000 mm and 1,300 mm.

The plant prefers full sun and is drought resistant.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The plant prefers a sandy, loamy soil that drains well.

It will tolerate a pH that ranges from alkaline to acidic.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

The plant is propagated from cuttings and cleaned seed.

Seeds usually germinate between 7 and 14 days.

Seedlings and young plants are sensitive to frost.

It requires a moderate amount of water for optimal growth.

The plant will achieve a moderate growth rate of 1 - 2m per year and will reach maturity between 4 and 5 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/carissa-edulis>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

ORANGE BIRD BERRY

Hoslundia opposita (L), orange bird berry, bird gooseberry, butterberry (E), uyaweyawe (X)

The plant is wide-spread throughout Southern Africa and typically found in savanna forest, on river-banks and in grasslands, up to 1,500m.

The fruits are single, 0.6cm in diameter, are borne in profusion from October to April, and are eaten raw.

The low-growing shrub may spread, but seldom exceeds 1m in height.

Its modest growth form, non-invasive root system and heavy fruiting, makes the plant ideal near dwellings, schools, water pipes, and power lines.

FRUITING SEASON				
Dec	Jan	Feb	☀️	
Mar	Apr	May	🍃	
Jun	Jul	Aug	❄️	
Sep	Oct	Nov	🦋	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit is rich in anti-oxidants that assist with overall good health and healing.

Leaves and fruits are rich in phytochemicals that yield essential oils for potential medicinal use.

Tender young leaves are cooked and eaten as a vegetable.

Leaves are used as a poultice, diuretic, and treatment for fever.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

A low growth form, shiny foliage and colourful fruit makes it a versatile ornamental plant suited for hedging and also as a living fence.

The leaves have an unpleasant scent that repels bees, which makes it good for collecting honey.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The flowers are frequented by bees and the fruit attracts various birds and animals.

The leaves are eaten by the larvae of butterflies.

Its ability to grow in rocky or sandy soils, makes it useful for soil stabilisation and combating erosion.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hoslundia-opposita>
 Photos: iNaturalist, Random Harvest,
 Wikimedia Commons

ORANGE BIRD BERRY

Hoslundia opposita (L), orange bird berry, bird gooseberry, butterberry (E), uyaweyawe (X)

The plant originates from Africa and occurs in the Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna biomes.

The plant supports biodiversity as an important food source: butterfly larvae browse the leaves, bees and other insects feed on the nectar, and birds and animals consume the fruit.

The plant is pollinated by bees and the seeds are naturally dispersed by the birds and animals that eat the fruit.

Because it attracts insects, birds and animals, plant it away from the house to keep friendly relations with the wildlife.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The plant prefers a warmer tropical and sub-tropical climate between 20°C and 35°C.

This shrub is best suited in areas of moderate to high rainfall.

It performs well in warmer positions in full sun.

It is not suited to colder areas that receive frost.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The plant can grow in a range of well-drained sandy soils.

It prefers a neutral pH of between 5 and 7.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Fresh seed sown from November to March should germinate easily between 2 and 4 weeks.

It can also be grown from stem cuttings treated with hormones, that strike relatively easily.

Young plants and seedlings need to be well-watered.

Growth is moderate and regular pruning will maintain shape and encourage new growth.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hoslundia-opposita>
 Photos: iNaturalist, Random Harvest,
 Wikimedia Commons

PORKBUSH

Portulacaria afra (L), porkbush, elephant's foot (E), igqwani'tsha (X)

The plant is found throughout the warmer parts of South Africa, typically on rocky slopes, scrub, thickets, bushveld and dry river valleys.

Porkbush is not known for its fruit, which is not edible, but the plant offers a host of medicinal and ecological benefits.

It is a evergreen shrub and seldom exceeds 3m. It is succulent in nature with a dense low-growing spread.

Its modest root system, canopy and height allows it to be planted near buildings, water pipes, power lines and roads.

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

- The plant helps lactating mothers to increase breast milk production.
- The leaves help to quench thirst, and treat exhaustion, dehydration and heat stroke.
- Chewing leaves treats sore throat and mouth infections.
- Juice is used to treat pimples and soothes rashes and stings.
- Crushed leaves provide relief to blisters and corns on the feet.
- The juice is used as antiseptic and as a treatment for sunburn.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

- The plant is a source of fodder for livestock.
- The nectar-rich flowers attract bees, perfect for beekeeping.
- It can be planted as an impenetrable hedge or security barrier.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

- The dense foliage makes an ideal nesting site for birds.
- It is used in erosion control and land reclamation.

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/portulacaria-afra>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

PORKBUSH

Portulacaria afra (L), porkbush, elephant's foot (E), igqwanitsha (X)

The porkbush originates in South Africa and occurs in the Albany thicket, fynbos, Indian Ocean coastal belt, Nama Karoo and Succulent Karoo biomes.

It plays a valuable role in the ecosystem as a food source for animals. It is heavily browsed by game, elephants, tortoises and domestic stock.

While seeds are dispersed by birds, vegetative propagation by means of cuttings throughout the year is highly successful.

It is visited by mammals and bees and should be planted away from the house.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

- It favours a warm, temperate climate from 10°C to 35°C.
- It is best suited in areas with a low annual rainfall.
- The shrub prefers to be planted in full sun but will also tolerate semi shade.
- It is a highly adaptive shrub that is frost resistant, as well as being able to withstand arid and semi-arid conditions.

SOIL CONDITIONS

- The shrub grows in most well-drained soils.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

- It is easily propagated from cuttings treated with hormones, as seed is not often available.
- Cuttings or truncheons strike root relatively easily, usually within 4 to 6 weeks.
- Young plants need very light watering.
- Once established, the plant grows rapidly before reaching maturity between 2 and 5 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/portulacaria-afra>

Photos: Glenice Ebedes,
Wikimedia Commons

RED IVORYWOOD

Berchemia zeyheri (L), red ivorywood (E), umnini (X)

The red ivorywood is primarily found in the northern parts of South Africa, Zimbabwe and Mozambique, in woodland, bushveld, rocky areas, along rivers, and streams.

The fruit is 1cm in diameter and forms in clusters from January to April and is eaten raw.

The tree grows up to 8m with medium to dense foliage.

With a moderately spreading root system, canopy and fruiting, the tree is suited for schools and public places.

FRUITING SEASON				
Dec	Jan	Feb	☀️	
Mar	Apr	May	🌿	
Jun	Jul	Aug	❄️	
Sep	Oct	Nov	🦋	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The raw fruit is rich in vitamin C, equivalent to an apple, and also contains vitamin B, to promote cellular and cardiac health.

It contains calcium, magnesium, iron, phosphorus, potassium and zinc for strengthening blood, bones and muscle.

It is a source of fibre for digestion and protein for strong muscles.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

It is a versatile plant that can grow into a valuable shade tree.

Its timber is used for fence poles and tools.

The tree can serve as a highly effective windbreak.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

This tree is a biodiversity powerhouse with its leaves, flowers, fruit and bark eaten by insects, birds and mammals.

It is evergreen to semi-deciduous and is drought-resistant.

The tree can be planted to control soil erosion.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/berchemia-zeyheri>
 Photos: Wikimedia Commons, iSpotnature

RED IVORYWOOD

Berchemia zeyheri (L), red ivorywood (E), umnini (X)

The tree originates in South Africa, Zimbabwe and Mozambique, and is typically found in the Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna biomes, often on the south- and east-facing slopes of mountains.

Its flowers are a food source for insects and the ripe fruit is enjoyed by birds, baboons, monkeys and bushbabies. The leaves are browsed by giraffes, eland, kudu, nyala, bushbuck and impala. Porcupines also eat the bark.

The seed is dispersed by fruit-eating birds.

Seed for planting can be extracted by removing the pulp from the ripened fruit.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The ideal temperature range is 22°C to 28°C, but will tolerate extremes of 15°C and 34°C.

It grows best under moderate to high rainfall conditions of 0-35mm per week.

The tree prefers to be planted in full sun.

The tree is sensitive to frost and will therefore need to be protected in colder climates.

SOIL CONDITIONS

It prefers well-drained sandy and loamy soils.

Optimal conditions require a neutral pH of 4 to 7.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Seeds in the ripe fruit pulp should be cleaned.

Fresh seed will germinate between 5 and 9 days.

Seedlings and young plants require little watering.

The plant achieves moderate annual growth under regular watering conditions.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/berchemia-zeyheri>
 Photos: Wikimedia Commons, iSpotnature

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RIVER BUSHWILLOW

Combretum erythrophyllum (L), river bushwillow (E), umdubu (X)

The river bushwillow occurs in Southern Africa, in areas of dry woodland or savanna, especially on river banks, up to 1,500m.

The 1-1.5cm poisonous seeds borne in clusters in summer are used to make dye. The unique 4-wing seeds remain on the tree for some time, enhancing its ornamental appeal.

The tree is fast-growing, up to 5m and produces a medium canopy.

A modest height and spread, low leaf litter and low root intensity, makes it suitable to be planted near buildings, roads and water and power lines.

Planting considerations

SEEDING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The tree's seeds and roots are considered poisonous but are sometimes used as a purgative and treatment of venereal disease.

Care must be taken when using this plant for medicinal purposes, as it is poisonous and can cause hiccups.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

A dark brown liquid is extracted from the roots, and is used to make dyes for the tanning industry.

The wood is used in construction and for making carvings, fence posts and tools.

Its lovely shape, beautiful bark and colourful autumnal foliage makes it a popular ornamental tree with ecological benefits.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The flowers attract wasps and the seed is eaten by birds.

The fast-growing tree offers shade, shelter, and can be planted as a windbreak.

The adaptable tree is low maintenance, water-wise and will tolerate drought conditions.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/combretum-erythrophyllum>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, iSpotnature

SGP The GEF
Small Grants
Programme

RIVER BUSHWILLOW

Combretum erythrophyllum (L), river bushwillow (E), umdubu (X)

The tree originates in Southern Africa and is typically found in Albany thicket, Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna biomes.

It has a moderate biodiversity value, as wasps and birds consume the fruit, and the foliage is browsed by giraffe and elephant.

Pollination is performed primarily by wasps who sometimes lay their eggs in the seed.

The plant produces lots of seed that sets easily, and many seedlings may be found under the tree.

Because the tree is visited by wasps, be sure to plant it away from the house.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

- The plant can tolerate a range of climates and prefers a warm to tropical temperature of 10°C - 35°C.
- Moderate annual rainfall is required for optimal growth.
- The plant prefers to be planted in full sun and will also tolerate light partial shade.
- The tree is drought and frost tolerant: flexy is sexy.

SOIL CONDITIONS

- The tree tolerates a diverse range of soil types – loam, sandy and clay.
- A pH range of 5 - 7 is preferred for optimum growing conditions.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

- It can be grown from fresh seed that should be soaked overnight before planting.
- Seeds will germinate between 7 and 14 days.
- Make sure to keep seedlings and young plants moist, but not wet.
- The fast-growing tree will reach maturity after 3 years in good growing conditions.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/combretum-erythrophyllum>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, iSpotnature

SEPTEE TREE

Cordia caffra (L), septee tree, saucer-berry (E), umlovulovu, umnovunovu, umnofunofu (X)

The tree occurs along the eastern seaboard of South Africa in dune bush and coastal forest, and further inland, in woodland and on forest margins.

While the orange-coloured 1cm fruit borne in clusters in summer are edible, the tree is more useful for its medicinal and timber purposes.

The hardy tree grows to an average height of 6m with a drooping habit.

A modest canopy and root system and moderate height makes the tree suitable for planting near buildings and electricity and water infrastructure.

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit has one of the highest potassium levels of wild edible plants that boosts muscle function and heart health.

It contains calcium, magnesium, and iron that promote muscle function, bone health, and other metabolic processes.

Parts of the tree are used to treat sore eyes, fever, and wounds.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The wood is used for fence posts and construction material, and the durable pink heartwood makes beautiful furniture.

With its distinctive bark, the tree is popular as an ornamental plant with ecological benefits.

Dry sticks rubbed together are used for fire-making.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The tree attracts pollinating insects and birds to the garden.

When trimmed and shaped it can be used as a sturdy hedge or as a privacy screen.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/cordia-cafra>
 Photos: Glence Ebedes, PlantZAfrica,
 Wikimedia Commons

SEPTEE TREE

Cordia caffra (L), septee tree, saucer-berry (E), umlovulovu, umnovunovu, umnofunofu (X)

The tree originates in northern South Africa and southern Botswana and is primarily found in the Albany thicket, Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna biomes.

The tree has a medium biodiversity relations with the flowers attracting insects and the fleshy fruit that is eaten by birds.

The flowers are pollinated by insects, primarily honeybees and the seeds are dispersed by fruit-eating birds.

The deciduous tree can be planted where you need sun in winter and shade in summer.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The plant tolerates a temperature climate range of 10°C to 35°C.

It grows best with annual rainfall between 800mm and 1,200 mm, and has a modest tolerance for dry conditions.

The plant prefers full sun and will tolerate partial shade.

SOIL CONDITIONS

It grows in well-drained, sandy and loam soils.

A slightly acidic pH range between 5 and 7 is most suitable.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

It can be grown from clean seed dried in the shade, scarified and soaked overnight before sowing.

Seeds will germinate around 14 days.

Cuttings can also be taken from hard and semi-hard branches in spring and summer, and treated with hormones.

The plant has an annual growth rate of about 550mm and reaches maturity after at least 5 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit <https://pza.sanbi.org/cordia-caffra>

Photos: Glenice Ebedes, PlantZAfrica, Wikimedia Commons

STAR -APPLE

Diospyros lycioides (L), star-apple, bluebush, monkey plum (E), umbhongisa (X)

The star-apple is found throughout Southern Africa, near water courses, in forests, and thickets up to 1,000m.

The single 2cm fruits are produced from January to June and are consumed raw, juiced, or in a jam.

The plant grows either into a shrub or small tree, to an average height of 3m.

Its moderate height, canopy spread, root system and low leaf litter allows the shrub to be planted near power lines, water pipes, roads and dwellings.

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

It is a rich source of vitamins A and C, twice that of oranges, to promote cellular function and immunity.

It contains calcium, phosphorus and iron for muscular and blood health.

The fruit is used to make beer and seeds can be substituted for coffee.

The roots are chewed to treat colds and coughs.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The shrub is valued for its shade and shelter and can be planted as a windbreak.

The wood is used for fence posts, making spoons, toys, construction materials, and furniture.

A yellow-brown dye is extracted from the roots and the bark is used for tanning skins.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

It is a valuable source of nectar for insects, especially bees, and fruit for birds.

The shrubby growth form provides habitat to wildlife.

The hardy shrub is water-wise and will tolerate drought conditions.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/diospyros-lycioides>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist,
 Wikimedia Commons

STAR -APPLE

Diospyros lycioides (L), star-apple, bluebush (E), umbhongisa (X)

The plant originates in Southern Africa and is commonly found in Albany thicket, fynbos, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, savanna, Succulent Karoo and Nama Karoo biomes.

The hardy plant promotes biodiversity as a valuable food source for various insects, birds, dassies and monkeys.

The shrub is dioecious, with each individual plant only producing either male or female flowers, relying on insects to pollinate the flowers.

It is therefore best to plant multiple individuals close together to promote fruiting.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

- The plant is suited to a warm and temperate range of climates from 10°C to 35°C.
- It is best suited in areas that receive moderate annual rainfall.
- The shrub prefers to be planted in full sun is drought-tolerant.

SOIL CONDITIONS

- The shrub grows in a range of well-drained soils.
- Optimal conditions require a neutral pH of 4 to 7.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

- It can be grown from seeds that are soaked in hot water overnight before being planted.
- Seeds will germinate between 18 and 20 days.
- The shrub has medium water requirements for optimal growth.
- Pinching out the branch tips of young plants will encourage a bushy plant.
- The slow-growing plant will reach maturity after 4 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/diospyros-lycioides>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist,
 Wikimedia Commons

THORNY GARDENIA

Hyperacanthus amoenus (L), thorny gardenia (E), uthongothi (X)

The plant is found on the east coast of Southern Africa, typically on open hillsides, in scrub bush, moist wooded kloofs and forests.

The fruits are single, about 1.5cm in diameter, are borne from March to October and are eaten raw.

The spiny, woody shrub grows up to 3m, with a multi-stemmed structure and branches growing at right angles to the trunk.

With a moderate growth habit and low root and leaf-litter intensity, the shrub is suitable for planting near buildings, roads, water pipes and power lines.

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit contains many antioxidants that promote good health and healing.

The roots and fruits are used for traditional medical purposes to treat stomach complaints and for cleansing.

The shrub is sometimes used as a treatment against fever.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The timber is used to produce fibres, fence posts, small tools and as fuelwood.

Pruned often, its spiny, dense foliage makes a good hedge or screen.

Its glossy green leaves and fragrant white flowers make it a popular ornamental plant.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

It is a valuable source of nectar for insects, especially bees, and fruit for birds.

It can be planted as a live fence to keep livestock out.

The leaves are browsed by many game species.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hyperacanthus-amoenus>

Photos: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

THORNY GARDENIA

Hyperacanthus amoenus (L), thorny gardenia (E), uthongothi (X)

The plant originates in Southern Africa and is commonly found in the Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna biomes.

The plant supports the ecosystem as a food source for birds and monkeys that eat the fruit, and for mammals that browse the leaves.

Pollination is performed by insects, including bees and butterflies, and seeds are dispersed by birds and animals.

Because it attracts insects, birds and animals, plant it away from the house to keep friendly relations with the wildlife.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

- The shrub is best suited to a tropical and sub-tropical climate of between 10°C and 35°C.
- It grows well in areas of moderate summer rainfall.
- The shrub favours areas with shade or semi-shade but will also tolerate full sun.
- The hardy shrub is drought tolerant and can withstand moderate frost.

SOIL CONDITIONS

- The plant prefers loam and tolerates most well-drained soils that retain some moisture.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

- Seeds should be cleaned before sowing.
- Germination takes about 8 weeks with a low success rate.
- Stem cuttings from a mature plant treated with hormones may yield greater success.
- Young plants and seedlings should be well-watered.
- Growth is slow, 50cm per year and reaches maturity after 3 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/hyperacanthus-amoenus>

Photos: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

TRANSVAAL RED MILKWOOD

Mimusops zeyheri (L), Transvaal red milkwood, red milkwood (E)

The tree occurs in the tropical and northern parts of South Africa, and is found on rocky outcrops, wooded hillsides, riverine and forest fringes and in open, dry woodland and bushveld.

The 1cm fruit is borne in clusters from April to September and is eaten raw.

The tree can reach 8m with a medium spreading canopy.

With a non-aggressive root system, and moderate growth form, the tree can be planted near water pipes as well as public spaces.

FRUITING SEASON				
Dec	Jan	Feb	☀️	
Mar	Apr	May	🌿	
Jun	Jul	Aug	❄️	
Sep	Oct	Nov	🌸	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit is a rich source of Vitamin C, the equivalent of an orange, for overall health and immunity.

It contains calcium, phosphorus and potassium to boost bone, blood and cellular health.

It contains amino acids, which all body cells need to perform their functions.

A bark decoction is used to treat wounds and ulcers.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The large evergreen tree can grow into a valuable shade tree or planted as a windbreak.

The timber is used for making fence poles and tools.

With its glossy, dark leaves, neat crown and sweet flowers it is a popular ornamental tree.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The tree is a magnet for numerous birds, insects and animals that eat the fruit and disperse the seed.

The tree can be used for erosion control in degraded lands.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/mimusops-zeyheri>
 Photos: Glance Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

TRANSVAAL RED MILKWOOD

Mimusops zeyheri (L), Transvaal red milkwood, red milkwood (E)

The tree originates from the tropical and northern region of South Africa. It occurs in the Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna biomes.

It is a biodiversity powerhouse as a food plant for birds, monkeys and antelope that eat the fruit, and for butterfly larvae that eat the leaves.

The flowers are pollinated by insects and the seed is naturally dispersed by the birds and animals that eat the fruit.

Heavy fruiting results in high wildlife visits and the tree should therefore be planted away from the house.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

- The tree prefers a temperature climate with a range between 15°C and 25°C.
- It is best suited in areas with a low annual rainfall.
- It prefers full sun and will tolerate semi-shade.
- The tree is sensitive to frost and will require protection in colder areas.

SOIL CONDITIONS

- The tree grows in various soils that are well drained.
- It prefers soils with a neutral pH of between 5 and 7.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

- Fresh seeds sown soonest are the most viable.
- Stored seed germinates better if scarified prior to sowing.
- Seeds germinate readily in about 2 weeks.
- Young plants and seedlings should be well watered.
- The fast-growing tree will mature in about 3 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/mimusops-zeyheri>
 Photos: Glence Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

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TREE FUCHSIA

Halleria lucida (L), tree fuchsia, white olive (E), umbinza (X)

The tree fuchsia is found throughout Southern Africa and occurs mostly in scrub, forest, ravines, mountain slopes, and near water courses.

The tree produces 10mm round fruit in clusters that is edible but not that tasty, and are mostly consumed by birds.

The evergreen tree typically reaches 5m but can grow up to 10m, with drooping branches and a dense, spreading canopy.

A moderate root system, low leaf litter and fruit intensity makes the tree suitable near buildings, water lines and roads.

FRUITING SEASON			
Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit contains phosphorous which is a key element of bones, teeth and cell membranes.

It contains amino acids, which all body cells need to perform their functions.

Extracts of the tree are used to make drops to treat ear ache and other body pains.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The flowers and fruits attract a variety of birds to the garden.

The timber is used for fuelwood, and in the making of fence poles and small tools.

It can be planted as a windbreak and makes a good shade tree.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The plant's nectar-rich flowers attract pollinating insects and birds.

The leaves are browsed by some game and livestock.

The low-maintenance, hardy tree is drought and frost resistant; flexy is sexy.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/halleria-lucida>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

TREE FUCHSIA

Halleria lucida (L), tree fuchsia, white olive (E), umbinza (X)

The plant originates from Southern Africa and occurs in the Albany thicket, fynbos, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, Nama Karoo, savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes.

It is a valuable pollinator plant for birds and bees, and other insects also feed on the flowers. The fruit is eaten by birds, and the leaves are browsed by buck and game.

The flowers are pollinated by bees and the seed is dispersed by birds feeding on the fruit.

Because it attracts many bees, birds and other insects, plant it away from the house.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The plant tolerates a range of temperatures, from 10°C to 35°C.

The plant benefits from moderate watering, but can withstand periodic dry spells.

It grows in full sun but tolerates semi shade.

SOIL CONDITIONS

It prefers a sandy loam, but will tolerate other well-draining soils.

It prefers a pH ranging from acidic to neutral, between 6 and 7.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Seeds can be sown from September - December and from March - May.

Cuttings and truncheons treated with hormone powder can be sown, and placed in a propagator with intermittent mist.

Seeds usually germinate within 2 to 6 weeks.

New plants require moderate watering.

The fast-growing tree will reach maturity in about 2 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/halleria-lucida>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes

TURKEY BERRY

Canthium inerme (L), turkey berry (E), umvutshwama, umyushulube, umvuthwamini (X)

The turkey berry occurs across South Africa in habitats ranging from coastal and montane forest, dune forest and forest margins, to bushveld and rocky grasslands, up to 1,700m

The fruits form in clusters, each fruit is about 1cm in diameter and these are eaten raw.

The tree reaches a height of 14m with a medium canopy.

Due to its moderate growth habit and root system, the tree can be planted around power and water lines as well as near buildings and roads.

Planting considerations

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit is a good source of vitamins C and E that contribute to skin and bone health, and boost immunity.

It contains a number of rare trace elements that help most bodily functions.

The leaves are sometimes used in the treatment of stomach ailments.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The tree serves as an effective windbreak and shelter for livestock.

The hard, tough wood is used to make fence poles, furniture and implements.

Its evergreen nature and attractive foliage attract many birds and insects throughout the year.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

With its spiky thorns and compact nature, it can be planted as a live fence to keep livestock out.

It can withstand tough conditions and is drought-resistant.

The fast-growing tree can be planted for erosion control.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/canthium-inerme>
 Photos: Wikimedia Commons, iNaturalist

TURKEY BERRY

Canthium inerme (L), turkey berry (E), umvutshwama, umyushulube, umvuthwamini (X)

The turkey berry originates from Southern Africa and is well-spread across the region. It occurs in the fynbos, grassland, savanna, Nama Karoo and Succulent Karoo biomes.

The plant has a high ecological value making it a valuable garden specimen. Its flowers provide pollen and nectar to bees and its fruit feeds birds and bush pigs.

The tree is pollinated by insects and its seed is spread by fruit-eating birds.

The seed can be extracted by removing the pulp from the ripened fruit.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The plant grows best in a temperate environment and can withstand some frost.

The tree does well in moderate rainfall areas and cannot survive arid conditions.

The tree grows best in full sun but will tolerate semi-shade.

SOIL CONDITIONS

This adaptable tree is best suited to well-drained, sandy, clay, and loamy soils.

It can grow in acid, neutral, and alkaline soil.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Propagation is easy and is best grown from ripe and cleaned seed.

Germination may take 2-3 months, followed by rapid growth.

While young, keep the seedlings moist, but not wet.

Allow seedlings to grow for at least 2-3 weeks before planting out.

It has a fast growth rate, reaching several metres within few years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/canthium-inerme>
 Photos: Wikimedia Commons, iNaturalist

SGP The GEF
Small Grants
Programme

UMZIMBEET

Millettia grandis (L), umzimbeet (E), umsimbeeti (X)

The tree occurs in KwaZulu-Natal and the Eastern Cape and is common in Pondoland, up to 600m.

The fruit is borne in the form of large 15cm oblong pods containing seeds which are not edible and are poisonous.

The fast-growing tree can reach a height of 10m with a large, spreading canopy.

The tree's height and canopy makes it unsuitable near power lines, roads or walls, but its low root intensity and low leaf litter allows it to be planted near schools and water pipes.

Planting considerations

SEEDING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The seed is not consumed as the seeds are poisonous.

The powdered root can be used as a poison for fish arrows, but the fish must be boiled before eating.

Ground seeds (used with caution) are soaked in milk and used in the treatment of roundworm.

A root mixture that has a calming, tranquilising effect is sometimes used to encourage sleep.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The wood is used for furniture, fence poles, planks and small tools.

The immense canopy makes it a perfect shade or shelter tree.

The attractive wood is used to make walking sticks for the tourist market.

The tree's root nodules help fix nitrogen in the soil.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

Seed pods provide a habitat for breeding butterflies.

The trees can be planted in a row as a living fence or windbreak.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/millettia-grandis>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

UMZIMBEET

Millettia grandis (L), umzimbeet (E), umsimbeeti (X)

The umzimbeet originates in KwaZulu-Natal and the Eastern Cape and is found in the Indian Ocean coastal belt biome.

The tree contributes to the ecosystem as a food source for butterfly larvae that feed on the leaves and baboons that strip and eat the bark.

The tree's nectar-rich flowers are easily pollinated by insects. The seeds form in pods from February to July, and are naturally distributed by wind and water.

This semi-deciduous, spreading tree will need to be planted in wide open spaces.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

- The tree grows best in a tropical or sub-tropical climate with a range of 10°C - 35°C.
- Wetter conditions in high rainfall areas are preferred.
- The tree favours full sun but will tolerate partial shade.
- The hardy tree is able to withstand some frost.

SOIL CONDITIONS

- The tree grows best in sandy and loamy soils.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

- The tree is easily propagated by fresh seed.
- Fresh seed should be soaked in warm water overnight before being sown, and tend to germinate quite readily.
- Young plants should be watered regularly.
- The fast-growing tree can achieve a growth rate of 80cm - 1m per year under optimum conditions.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/millettia-grandis>

Photos: Glenice Ebedes,
Wikimedia Commons

WATER BERRY

Syzygium cordatum (L), water berry, water pear (E), injomi, umdoni (X)

The tree is found in central and southern Africa near fresh water, along watercourses and stream banks, in forests, and riverine thickets.

The 1cm fruits are produced in abundant clusters from December to April and are eaten raw.

The large attractive tree reaches a height of 15m with an extensive canopy.

Its height, spreading canopy, aggressive root system and intense fruiting render it unsuitable to be planted near buildings, roads and utility infrastructure.

Planting considerations

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit packs a punch with high levels of vitamins A, B, C and E to boost human cellular functions.

The fruit is a good source of iron, magnesium, and potassium that strengthen bones, blood, and muscles.

The bark has medical properties to treat diarrhoea, stomach problems, headaches, amenorrhoea, wounds and respiratory problems.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS AND FIELDS

The timber is used for making fence posts and tools.

The large spreading canopy makes a valuable shade tree for shelter.

The fruit and bark is used to produce a blue dye.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The tree withstands water logging and is used to arrest erosion along water courses.

The tree is resistant to fire and can be planted as a windbreak.

The tree is believed to indicate underground water.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/syzygium-cordatum>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes,
 Wikimedia Commons

WATER BERRY

Syzygium cordatum (L), water berry, water pear (E), injomi, umdoni (X)

The water berry originates in Southern and Central Africa and grows in the Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna biomes.

Several bird species feast on the fruit, insects are attracted to the flowers and the fruit and leaves are consumed by animals.

Flowers are pollinated by birds and other insects, and seeds are dispersed by the birds and animals that eat the fruit.

Because the tree attracts many species of birds, insects and animals, be sure to plant it away from the house.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree tolerates a temperate climate with temperature variations from 10°C to 35°C.

The tree does well with an annual rainfall of between 600mm and 1,500mm and can withstand a fair amount of water logging.

It prefers full sun or morning sun and will tolerate semi shade.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The tree grows best in sandy or loam soil.

It prefers soils with a pH level between 5 and 7.5.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Propagation is best with highly viable fresh seed that must not be dried.

Fresh seeds take about 25 days to germinate.

Young plants and seedlings require to be watered regularly.

Growth rate is fast and can achieve 1m per year in under optimal growing conditions.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/syzygium-cordatum>

Photos: Glenice Ebedes,
Wikimedia Commons

WILD DATE PALM

Phoenix reclinata (L), wild date palm (E), isundu (X)

The wild date palm is found across Southern Africa, and occurs along rivers and swamps across northern and eastern South Africa.

The fruits form profusely in clusters, each fruit about 2.5cm in diameter, between February and April, and can be eaten raw or juiced.

The tree grows about 5m high with a large spreading canopy.

It has moderate root intensity and leaf litter, making it compatible to plant near houses, roads, and power lines, but away from water pipes due to the heavy fruiting.

FRUITING SEASON				
Dec	Jan	Feb		
Mar	Apr	May		
Jun	Jul	Aug		
Sep	Oct	Nov		

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

- The fruit contains vitamins A, B and C to promote health and immunity.
- It has calcium, iron, magnesium, and phosphorus that strengthen bones, blood, and muscles.
- It is rich in amino acids, which all body cells need to function.
- The fruit is tapped for milk that is fermented for alcoholic beverages.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

- The palm provides shade and can also be planted as a windbreak.
- The fibre of the leaf fronds can be used to make baskets, brooms, hats, mats and roofs.
- The leaves are used to make skirts worn by Xhosa boys during their initiation rites.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

- Makes an excellent living hedge to keep livestock out.
- The hardy plant tolerates frost and waterlogging and is also drought resistant.
- The tree is useful for stabilising the soil and combating riverine erosion.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/phoenix-reclinata>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

WILD DATE PALM

Phoenix reclinata (L), wild date palm (E), isundu (X)

The plant originates on the east coast of Southern Africa and is found in the savanna biome.

Butterfly larvae eat the leaves, and birds, monkeys, and antelope consume the fruit.

The flowers are pollinated by insects, and birds and animals disperse the seed.

The tree is dioecious, with separate male and female trees. Be sure to plant the tree in clumps, in full sun to promote pollination and fruiting.

The spreading tree will require wide, open space to grow to its full potential.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree prefers a warm climate and can tolerate temperature variations from 15°C to 35°C.

It thrives in areas with moderate to high annual rainfall of 500mm to 1,500mm.

It prefers full sun and will tolerate semi shade, but will not produce fruit under shaded conditions.

SOIL CONDITIONS

It tolerates seasonal waterlogging, dry conditions and poor soil.

It prefers to grow in a pH level between 5 and 7.5.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

The tree can be propagated from cleaned seeds.

Seeds germinate between 2 and 3 months.

Suckers can also be taken from an adult plant strike easily.

Young plants and seedlings need to be well-watered.

It achieves moderate growth and reaches maturity after 5 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/phoenix-reclinata>
 Photos: Glenice Ebedes, iNaturalist

WILD MEDLAR

Vangueria infausta (L), wild medlar (E), amavilo (X)

The tree is found throughout the south-eastern region of South Africa, in grassland, thicket and open woodlands, often on termite mounds, in rocky places and dunes, up to 1,500m.

The single 2cm apple-flavoured fruits are borne from March to October and are eaten raw, juiced or in a jam.

The small tree grows up to 5m with a medium canopy, and often with a multi-stem trunk.

Its moderate root system, canopy and height allows it to be planted near buildings, roads and utility infrastructure.

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fleshy fruit is rich in Vitamin C, equivalent to orange, to boost immunity.

It is a rich source of calcium, iron, magnesium, and potassium for bone, blood and overall health.

It contains fibre, protein and amino acids for a healthy digestive system.

The roots are used in malaria and pneumonia treatment.

A decoction of the leaves is used as a purgative and a leaf poultice is used for dental, abdominal and menstrual pain.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

The leaves are used as fodder for livestock.

The timber is used for fuelwood, and for fence poles and tools.

The hardy tree is frost and drought resistant; flexy is sexy.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

The tree is a valuable food source for insects, birds and mammals.

The tree's hardiness and adaptability makes it useful for erosion control.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/vangueria-infausta>
 Photos: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

WILD MEDLAR

Vangueria infausta (L), wild medlar (E), amavilo (X)

The medlar originates in Africa and is found in the Albany thicket, fynbos, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt, Nama Karoo, savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes.

The tree is a valuable source of food for butterfly larvae that eat the leaves, monkeys and other small mammals that devour the fruit, and for buck that browse the leaves.

Flowers are pollinated by insects and seeds are dispersed by birds and monkeys.

Propagation is by means of seeds and cuttings and seeds can be stored up to a year.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree prefers to grow in a mild to temperate climate, with ranges from 12°C to 36°C.

It grows best with annual rainfall between 700mm to 1,500mm.

It prefers full sun and will tolerate semi-shade.

It is adaptable and can withstand drought and frost.

SOIL CONDITIONS

It prefers to grow in a sandy, loamy soils.

The tree thrives in soils with a pH between 5 and 7.5.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

It can be grown from fresh or stored seed sown in summer.

Cuttings treated with hormones taken from semi-hard wood and suckers from the base of the tree strike relatively easy.

New plants require moderate watering.

The tree achieves a moderate growth rate up to 50cm per year.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/vangueria-infausta>
 Photos: iNaturalist, Wikimedia Commons

WILD PLUM

Harpephyllum caffrum (L), wild plum (E), umgwenya(X)

The tree is found along the eastern regions of South Africa and typically occurs in riverine forest up to 1,400m.

The 2.5cm in diameter fruits form profusely in clusters, between March and June, and can be eaten raw, juiced or in jams and jellies.

The tree can reach a height of 7m and spreads a moderate canopy.

Due to its moderate leaf litter and root intensity, it can be planted near buildings and roads and around utility infrastructure.

FRUITING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

FOR YOUR HEALTH AND NUTRITION

The fruit contains as much vitamin C as in oranges and vitamin B to boost health and immunity.

It contains important rare trace elements that are not easy to find in other foods.

An infusion from the bark is used to treat skin, muscle and bone ailments in traditional medicine.

Applied to the skin, the bark is also used to treat acne and eczema

Powdered burnt bark is used to treat sprains and bone fractures.

FOR GARDENS, FARMS, AND FIELDS

It can grow into a valuable shade tree and can also be planted as a windbreak.

The wood is used for making fence poles, tools, furniture, beams and also for carving curios.

FOR THE ENVIRONMENT

Mammals like buck, bushbabies, and monkeys eat its fruits and spread the seeds.

It is useful for soil stabilisation and combating erosion.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/garcinia-livingstonei>
 Photos: iNaturalist, PlantZAfrica,
 Wikimedia Commons

WILD PLUM

Garcinia livingstonei (L), African mangosteen (E), amabimbi (X)

The Wild Plum originates along the east coast of Southern Africa and is found in the Albany thicket, grassland, Indian Ocean coastal belt and savanna, biomes.

The fruit is eaten by birds, bushbabies, monkeys, baboons and bushbuck. Butterfly and moth larvae feed on the leaves.

The tree is dioecious with separate male and female flowers on different plants. Multiple trees grown together will promote fruiting.

The flowers are pollinated by insects, and seeds are dispersed by birds and animals.

Ecosystem associations

Planting considerations

PLANTING SEASON

Dec	Jan	Feb	
Mar	Apr	May	
Jun	Jul	Aug	
Sep	Oct	Nov	

ATMOSPHERIC GROWING CONDITIONS

The tree thrives in a tropical and sub-tropical climate between 20°C and 35°C.

It prefers full sun but will tolerate some shade.

The tree is not suited to cold areas and is sensitive to frost.

SOIL CONDITIONS

The tree can grow in a range of soils.

Soils with a neutral PH are best suited to the tree.

HOW TO GROW THE PLANT

Seeds should be soaked overnight in water and scrubbed.

Seeds germinate fairly rapidly within 7 to 11 days.

It can also be propagated from truncheons that have been shade-dried before planting. These strike relatively easily.

The tree thrives in well-watered conditions.

The tree is fast-growing up to 1.5m per year and matures into a 7 m specimen at 2 - 3 years.

Please pick plant parts carefully to avoid damage, always leave some fruits for plants to reproduce, and beware of contamination.

For more information visit
<https://pza.sanbi.org/garcinia-livingstonei>
 Photos: iNaturalist, PlantZAfrica,
 Wikimedia Commons

